

VOLUMETRIC ESTIMATION OF SILVER IN COPPER—SILVER
MIXTURES CONTAINING MORE THAN 50% COPPER
BY VOLHARD'S METHOD

BY R. P. SHUKLA AND R. P. BHATNAGAR

Volumetric estimation of Ag in Cu-Ag mixtures containing more than 50% Cu has been made by first separating the bulk of Cu from the mixture by ion-exchange method and then estimating the whole of silver by Volhard's method.

No convenient method is known for the volumetric estimation of silver in mixtures containing silver and copper, having copper more than 50%. According to Scott (*"Standard Methods of Analysis"*, 1950, p. 824) the titration by Volhard's method cannot be done when copper is over 60%. According to Sutton (*"A Systematic Hand Book of Volumetric Analysis"*, 1935, p. 141) this method of estimating silver can be used in presence of copper below 70%. Vogel (*"A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis"*, 1951, p. 256) states that copper does not interfere provided that it does not form more than 40% of the alloy.

Treadwell and Hall (*"Analytical Chemistry"*, 1935, p. 652) have recommended a procedure of estimating silver in such mixtures. According to them if more than 50% copper is present, the following procedure should be adopted.

"Precipitate the silver by means of an excess of alkali thiocyanate, filter, wash completely with water, then dissolve the silver thiocyanate in concentrated nitric acid by boiling for an hour. As the sulphuric acid formed will have some influence on the titration, barium nitrate solution is added to precipitate it completely and then titration done to estimate silver". This method therefore requires more than two hours for a single estimation. The main difficulty here is the presence of the excess of copper in the mixture of copper and silver as nitrates. A quick procedure to lessen the percentage of copper is the chief aim in this paper. Hence, the present work has been undertaken to separate the bulk of copper by ion-exchange method and then to ascertain if the estimation can be done by Volhard's method.

The work done by the present authors [*Agra Univ. J. Res. (Science)*, 1954, 3, 9] on the effective separation of copper from silver-copper mixtures shows that silver has a preferential exchange on sulphonated coal resin as compared to copper and that a suitable column can be prepared to exchange all the silver present in an aliquot volume of the mixture, leaving just a very small part of the resin for copper exchange. Such a process minimises the presence of copper in the mixture to a negligible extent as far as the interference in the estimation of silver by Volhard's method is concerned. Volhard's method can then be used with the usual efficiency to estimate silver, after it has been eluted from the column completely. As has been experienced by us, the method is quick and does not require much skill, if once a suitable column length, its break through capacity, flow rate, etc. are found out.

EXPERIMENTAL

Resin-sulphonated coal was prepared by the method adopted by Bafna, Pai and Shah (*Curr. Sci.*, 1951, 20, 233).

The resin was used in a column, prepared out of a 50. c.c. burette having a glass wool plug at the bottom and about 1.0 c.c. thick layer of fine sand above it. Preliminary experiments were conducted to find out the break through capacity of the column, and a suitable length was found out for the proper working. In our case, a column of 25 cm. in length and of cross-section of 1.0 sq. cm. was used. Each time a definite volume of the mixture was used in which the amount of silver was within the limits of break through capacity of the column. This ensured the complete exchange of silver present in a known volume of the solution meant for silver estimation. The resin was used in the hydrogen cycle. The column in the process retained all the silver ions present, leaving only a part of the space for copper exchange. The column was then washed with ion-free water so as to remove any adhering copper ions. The resin was regenerated with 6.0% HNO₃. The eluted solution contained all the silver ions with only negligible number of copper ions, even when silver was only 5% and copper 95% by weight in the mixture. Hence, it was possible to estimate silver by Volhard's method in the eluted silver solution. We, proceeding in this manner, were able to estimate silver by Volhard's method in solutions containing only 5% silver and the rest, copper. Our results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Resin-sulphonated coal. Column length = 15.0 cm. Column cross-section = 1.0 sq. cm. Flow rate = 5.0 ml./min. Titrant conc. = 0.1N-KCNS. Total column capacity = 4.25 m.e. of AgNO₃.

% Cu in mixture.	Calc. Ag.	*Ag found by Volhard's method.	% Error.	% Cu in mixture.	Calc. Ag.	*Ag found by Volhard's method.	% Error.
37.92	0.10788 g.	0.10788 g.	0.00	70.00	0.02157 g.	0.02157 g.	0.00
46.60	0.04315	0.04315	0.00	74.60	0.01795	0.01799	0.36
54.40	0.03592	0.03613	0.60	80.00	0.01348	0.01348	0.00
59.30	0.03077	0.03071	0.14	84.01	0.01079	0.01079	0.00
64.50	0.02697	0.02697	0.00	58.32	0.00427	0.00421	0.15

* After applying ion-exchange method.

Thus, it will be seen that by the method of exchange chromatography all the disadvantages of the previous methods are eliminated and still the accuracy is maintained within $\pm 0.5\%$. Further comment is necessary on Sutton's method (*loc. cit.*) of estimation. To avoid sulphuric acid, he has suggested that it may be precipitated by the addition of barium nitrate and the barium sulphate need not be filtered. But our experience shows that if barium sulphate is not filtered and washed several times with water, the results become a little low, due to adsorption of some of the silver ions by barium sulphate.